

Case Study on Trade Union Establishment's Innovation of Shanghai Federation of Trade Unions

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Abstract

In order to solve the problem of the worker in joining trade unions and the formation rate of trade unions, Shanghai federation of trade unions strives to explore the solutions, then issued the "Tentative scheme of Shanghai federation of trade unions office about organizing employees to join trade unions outside the system of enterprise"(named "Tentative scheme" for short),and has achieved initial success. This paper summarizes the practice and experience of Shanghai federation of trade unions, finally it offers some suggestions for future work.

Keywords Union ; Tentative Scheme ; Independence.

1. Introduction

In recent years, more and more trade unions have been established ,they provide a strong guarantee for a further protect the legitimate rights and interests of workers .Trade unions are playing an increasingly important role in the establishment of harmonious labor relations, employee rights and interests, and promote the development of enterprises. Reilly & Denvir (2008) found that unions can improve employment relationships, performance and the ability to change. Ying Zhang (2014) pointed out that the more involvement of employees and trade unions in the work, the more they have the sense of identity to the organization, which is considered to be paid attention to in the organization, and the lower the turnover intention of the employees. Hongmei Shan (2014) use 433 employees of non-state-owned enterprises enterprises as the research sample, the results of the study show that, the union practice participation function, educational function and maintenance function is positively correlated with the business performance, and participation influence functions and educational functions on enterprise performance more significantly than the maintenance function, construction function and enterprise performance have no significant correlation. Therefore, enterprises should pay attention to the enterprise's trade union plays a role in the human resource management, enterprise should make full use of the complementary advantages of both work, strengthen the functions of human resource management, so as to improve the core competitiveness of enterprises.

However, with the increasingly prominent role of trade unions, the problems of trade unions can also not be ignored. Different with the foreign trade union, China's trade union is based on the enterprise, and has a strong dependence on the enterprise, many companies often hinder the establishment and development of trade unions for various reasons. In the aspects of personnel appointing, many union leaders are from the internal management of part-time, such as chairman of the union by Deputy Secretary of the Party committee secretary and concurrently, and some are even appointed by the vice general manager of human resources or, at the same time they also be on behalf of both groups stand. In economic terms, the "trade union law" stipulates: "enterprises, institutions, organizations of the Committee of full-time staff salaries, bonuses and subsidies paid by the unit", Obviously, the economy of the enterprises' trade unions is dependent on enterprises. It can be found that the biggest problem of China's trade unions is its independence, and the establishment of trade unions is the premise of the role of the trade union, so the most basic thing is the independence of trade unions. In accordance with the requirements of the government , trade unions at all levels adhere to the formation of trade unions and the development of membership as a top priority, to maximize the organization of workers to trade unions, and made significant progress. But there

are still a number of enterprises have long refused to support the workers' Union, and even interfere with and obstruct the workers' union. Although the Union and the government have many communication, but they can not change this dilemma. Finally, if the enterprise does not support, then the trade unions will not be able to set up a "vicious circle", which has become the biggest obstacle to the formation of trade unions.

Shanghai Federation of trade unions issued a "pilot scheme", which is the Shanghai Federation of trade unions' exploration for the issue of low rate of entry and the establishment of a low rate of labor unions, which is undoubtedly a significant reform. If the first union of Wal-Mart Walmart, and FOXCONN, the establishment of the first trade union with a typical case of meaning, the reform of the Shanghai trade union initiatives have the valuable value of institutional innovation. The following is a combination of the specific practice of Shanghai trade unions to explore how to better solve the problem of the formation of trade unions.

2. "Tentative Scheme"

2.1 Specific Implementation Methods

Shanghai federation of trade unions issued the "Tentative scheme of Shanghai federation of trade unions office about organizing employees to join trade unions outside the system of enterprise", Requirements in the enterprise system to develop the staff to join the union, the accumulation of a certain number of members, such as a single member of the enterprise to absorb more than 25 people, the company must be required to set up trade unions. Specific implementation methods are as follows:

2.1.1 Open Reception Point, So That Workers Can Find A "Door"

The total organization department and the municipal aid center cooperation in Shanghai City worked together, if the workers want to join the union, they can directly dial "12351", related operations can apply for membership, after the staff membership application according to the employee's business address or living area and then transferred to the union or street Town Union, the Union will be responsible for the relevant procedures. In order to facilitate the application of migrant workers to join in ,Trade unions have set up an application point near their work address and live address, and they will also use the network media, etc., such as the opening of the WeChat public number, APP, etc. As long as the workers sweep the two-dimensional code, or log on the phone application store to download, If the employees want to join the union, they can enter the APP, and then select "I get to" click, then fill in personal information data table, the trade unions in the streets of the town park and the employee's enterprises will contact the employees within 15 days after submitting the data table, and the trade unions will assist the employees to complete the following procedure. Online membership is so convenient. In this way, we can ensure that the online and offline dual channel line, allowing workers to join more convenient. Such as trade unions of Free Trade Zone choose to use We Chat to help the public to join the public, they set up a worker monomer into the window, the staff can click into the window and then learn a variety of membership related information. Trade unions of Yangpu District Federation had an innovation in the channels to join the union, employees can join the application through the Internet, service window and industry or regional trade unions, and through the association of comprehensive division will directly apply for membership. Pudong New Area set up a point of entry of the staff in the talent apartment of Tang Dynasty ,and Jiading District set up a reception point in the apartment in Chengcheng .

2.1.2 Set Up Reservoirs, So That Employees Can Have A "Home".

Through continuous exploration, the "Tentative scheme" draw a clear road map: according to the principle of proximity, to establish comprehensive division in regional and industrial trade unions , or relying on the Development Zone, building, village, migrant workers apartments, the street waiting for the union as a special absorption Enterprises outside the system workers into the "reservoir". Songjiang District Federation of trade unions in order to attract the majority of workers into the union, the commercial group in a more concentrated and developed service park which opened a joint trade unions, such as the new century Mediterranean, Thames town. And finally, through practice, to attract workers to join the trade unions, so that their enterprises to establish a trade union. Shanghai Software Park Federation of trade unions, belongs to the long march in Putuo District, established a comprehensive division of labor. After some of the company's employees to apply for admission to the park after the union, Shanghai Rong Mdt InfoTech Ltd administrative side of the application for the formation of trade unions expressed support for the attitude. Zhangjiang science and Technology Park in Pudong New Area, the Federation of trade unions set up a joint staff in Zhangjiang Tang talent apartment, they work together, and finally ,there have been thousands of employees outside the enterprise system to join the trade union organizations.

2.1.3 Implement The Institution , So That Employees Can Gain The Benefits.

Shanghai City Federation of trade unions at all levels must carry out the requirements in the vast majority of workers outside the system after the admission of monomer: apply for a membership card, a membership card and a membership service support plan, giving a manual rights to carry out a trade union activities. After the formal

establishment of the trade union, the membership of the staff must be transferred immediately. At the same time, the Union also asked the trade unions at all levels to carry out the activities of the cost of subsidies for employees. The cost of staff activities should cost by the city and district trade union trade union in accordance with the allocation of half way to each employee annual payment of 100 dollars into subsidies funds, in order to ensure the daily activities of workers outside the system of membership funds. At the same time, in order to encourage enterprises to participate in the trade unions at all levels, the City Federation of trade unions will be the first batch of pilot union subsidies, subsidies to them. Jingan District Federation of trade unions of enterprises outside the staff to carry out the "five to send" activities, that is," to send political concern, to send employment assistance, to send help in life, to send the protection of the interests ,to send cultural care of the delivery". Jiading District Federation of trade unions to improve the spirit of workers from the cultural aspects of the improvement, they opened a bookstore in Chengcheng migrant workers apartment, after the entry of workers can learn to read here. And the Jiading District Federation of trade unions on the spiritual and cultural aspects of the improvement is different, the Putuo District Federation of trade unions from the material aspects, to provide a free lunch benefits. And every month in the employees of the enterprise or residence, held a "please eat a meal, month lunch" activities, so that workers can really gain benefit.

2.2 The Security Mechanism

"Reform is forced by the problem arising". The formation of the work of trade unions, forced trade unions to form a system of reform and innovation. Only through reform, can we really solve the dilemma of the formation of trade unions from the source. Shanghai trade union issued the pilot approach is to carry out a reform. Through the "Tentative scheme" reform is not a temporary decision and a blood, but found the mature scheme.

First of all, the CPC Central Committee has repeatedly requested that the trade unions should strive to expand coverage and enhance representation. To three-dimensional, multi-level expansion of organizational coverage, the most widely organized into the trade unions. At the same time, in accordance with the administrative divisions, relying on grass-roots units to establish an organization to carry out the work at the same time, innovative grassroots organizations, members of the development, contact with the masses, to carry out activities." (anonymous, 2016) .Shanghai and the "Tentative scheme" is a response to the call of the Party Central Committee, propose solutions for the formation of work encountered in the business administration is not supported in the union, and even prevent workers forming a trade union, increase the enrollment rate of workers and formation rate of labor unions.

Secondly, the "trade union law" clearly provides that the union is a voluntary combination of working class mass organizations. The right to organize and join trade unions in accordance with the law is the basic rights of workers, and no unit or individual shall infringe upon them. Staff is the main body. The "trade union law" also stipulates that "blocking the employees to participate in and organize trade unions or obstruct the superior trade union to help guide the establishment of trade unions, the labor administrative department shall order correction; refuse to correct, the labor administrative departments may apply to the people's governments at and above the county level." Shanghai trade union is through the pilot approach, change forming a trade union rely on corporate governance to be forming a trade union around the workers , to solve the problem of the formation of trade unions according to the law , so that employees can join the union when they are outside the enterprise system monomer.

2.3 Significance of implementation

Trade union is the representative of the rights and interests of workers, is to safeguard the rights and interests of workers and employers to negotiate with the "negotiator", is in opposition to the management position (KangJing-ping, 2009) .The role of the trade union can be effectively played only when the trade union can truly represent the workers, and the government is relatively independent of the government. This means that if the union can't really become a worker's own organization, then it is meaningless to discuss the role of the trade union. The independence of trade unions in Chinese enterprises has always been a hindrance to the role of trade unions, and as the basic premise of the role of trade unions, the formation of trade unions has been concerned. If it is a step forward from the Unions outside the enterprise to independent trade unions (Figure), trade unions in this way have a long way to go, and the "Tentative scheme" of Shanghai Municipal Federation of trade unions will play a central role between them.

2.4 Actual Effect Analysis

Through the survey data can be found, with efforts to continuously explore the Shanghai trade unions, up to December 4, 2015,the Shanghai Federation of trade unions has been absorbed outside the system of membership of 3298 people, and forced 5 enterprises to establish trade unions, to attract members 10104 people. On July 21,2016,From the eight session of the thirteen session of the Federation of trade unions of Shanghai city was held (enlarged) meeting can be learned because of reform, Shanghai has the "implementation measures" effect has been strengthened, attracting more and more workers to join in, to the first half of 2016 has been directly outside the system to absorb the workers into more than 3000 at the same time, AND the two companies will be forced to build the union. Shanghai City, deputy director of the NPC Standing Committee, Municipal Federation of trade unions chairman Hong Hao said that since 2016, the Shanghai Municipal Federation of trade unions focus development zone, express logistics and other key areas and industries, deepening the migrant workers membership focused action, promote the enterprises outside the system of workers single membership, and forced the enterprise outside the system where the employee will, in the first half from outside the system of 3276 members, 2 companies will be forced to build the union. Among them, the sengon agency APP "I want to join the" column, through the way of online application, acceptance, examination and grading line, tracking, closed-loop management, more than 1100 employees have been joined the Union through the audit in more than 2 months .It can be seen that the reform of Shanghai has achieved remarkable results, and provide a solution for the the problem of the entry of workers and the build of trade unions in a certain extent.

3. Summary

The reform of trade unions in Shanghai has achieved good results, and accumulated a lot of experience, of course, in the course of the process also found some shortcomings which to be further improved.

3.1 Summarize Experience

3.1.1 Make Full Use of the New Media Platform

Through the use of new media platform, we can create more convenience for workers. As the development of the "Shanghai union sengon news agency APP, which contains a variety of channels will apply for membership, we can click on the button "I want to join" legitimate labor rights violations and click on "I will protect" button, want to participate in recreational activities, we can click on the "Happy Valley", and to mitigate the pressure at the end of the time "decompression the cabin" button and so on. At the same time, to face the problem of the number of employees, personnel scattered, we should make full use of new media, the union grid instructors on the monomer member under the jurisdiction of the establishment of We Chat group, strengthen communication with members, timely feedback to the member, in order to better manage.

3.1.2 Improve Service Quality

"Tentative scheme" Mainly to solve the problem of the majority of workers, the work should be done to the majority of workers as the center, to allow workers to feel the warmth of the trade union. On the one hand, the staff should strengthen their sense of service, to provide the necessary help and guidance for the staff outside the system. Only in this way, the majority of workers will be more active to join the union of the family, so as to improve the rate of Union and the formation rate of trade unions. On the other hand, at the same time to ensure the implementation of funding support. In addition to the unions provide subsidies, trade unions should vigorously strengthen the staff membership and single Small and micro businesses Union funding support, the budget management system and should be unified in management, in order to achieve the protection of the funds.

3.1.3 Effective Management

The number of enterprises in the new union members under 50 people are usually managed by the Small and micro businesses Federation of trade unions (Union grid station) , they should careful registration and management related information, and then by the trade union grid station comprehensive decomposition of the implementation level

management. After the unified acceptance of the trade union grid station, according to the principle of proximity to the nearest neighbor points to the work of various trade union grid, by the trade union grid instructor daily management. Its main task is to be responsible for the provision of membership registration, membership card issuance, trade union membership cards, membership services, and then turn the trade union membership management services. More than 50 members of the enterprise has established a trade union committee, the Federation of trade unions of small and micro enterprises.

3.2 Improvements

- i) Trade unions should be on the various aspects of the "Tentative scheme" to give a high degree of attention, and actively practice. Other departments have auxiliary effect on the implementation of the "Tentative scheme". for example, from the human resources department, trade test area law enforcement unit, property and other departments, so they should strengthen cooperation with them, in order to offer staff membership together and trade unions the problems and suggestions, to work together. At the same time, the higher level trade unions should speed up the legal protection of the entry of workers and the formation of trade unions, to ensure the legitimate entry of the majority of workers and the formation of trade unions.
- ii) Pay attention to publicity. The "Tentative scheme" is still in the exploratory stage, it should strengthen its publicity, so that more workers understand and participate in. On the one hand, we can use the Internet and other new media platforms, such as WeChat public numbers, as well as APP and other aspects of network publicity. At the same time, we can also join the project, network membership, service membership, membership and a variety of activities, so that employees can learn more about the union, so as to attract them to join the union.

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